

R The Searching for Thriving the China Twenty- Two Provinces' Income per capita in 2025 & Increasing the USA States' GDP Value by California~Texas States & Illinois~Florida States etc. Correspondingly through Sustainably Observing

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ABSTRACT: The USA GDP with top five states' variation status analysis would show 317~260 billion yuan by Massachusetts~Washington states accordingly explained the Massachusetts one strong economy strength and capacity in 2003 in light of this paper. The y-y value might indicate 4.2%~4.8% by them respectively recorded their modest growth step. In contrast, the Virginia one maintained the fastest step with 6.3%. On the other side, the China top 11 provinces' income per capita variation analysis in 2025 would show 35~42 thousand yuan by Shan'xi & Inner Mongolia respectively expressed their higher income. Moreover, all of those top 11 provinces surpassed the whole country average 3.5 thousand. Thereby, the high-tech production would occupy the most part for us to be pursuit the high-efficiency and high-level environment that might become our further destination for producing more innovation production continually. So that the enough educating new engineer and talents enable us to process more space for searching more functional ones with more diversities business. Because those diversities may make

our life to become more convenient and comfortable through endeavoring our engineers and experts for the sake of positively participating their each research theme and making an interesting conception under main principles. In USA the more sophisticated project will affect their GDP enhancement through widely collecting the world top scientists and scholars to process more deepening research and science that may occupy their first-one country with stabilized leading effectiveness. From California to Missouri state the higher GDP would reflect the entire nation quality and level through the aeronautics out-space exploration lunar landing etc. a series of scientific research are able to continually process that makes the USA to become No. 1 in all of the fields. Even they proceeded the Mars etc. approaching and rotating & landing works many years ago. Moreover, they owned the most amount nuclear weapons with several thousand that may destroy the whole earth once the nuclear war happens. So we should pay more attention to the USA who may affect its role in every aspects in the earth. Thereby, China will raise up becoming the second GDP big country who may prohibit USA military and limit its development and enlarging behavior too.

Keywords: *Searching for; thriving China Provinces' Income per capita; in 2025; the USA GDP Variation, Sustainably observing; Illinois~Florida.*

1. Introduction

The GDP which indicates national economic status has provided an important role in every aspect in the world. So that the population increasing rate would be maintained for the sake of raising high-technique product with the entire industrial chain constantly which might enhance our new-quality-productivity. Hence we should consider the effective factors for example the population quantity, new quality productivity with high-technique etc. like big plane electric vehicle battery AI robot quantum computer medicine making disease diagnosis AI (artificial intelligence) ocean source space exploration nuclear generator etc. other ones. Low population is enable to offer high life & quality with improving GDP per capita value. Meanwhile, it can enhance the national whole GDP value and help us to boost the economic recovery and many things to do. So the certain population is about to improve our

national confidence some degree and make us to become priority one as early as possible even the super-country to lead the world to leadership right.

In contrast, the GDP increasing rate may play a significant role with regulating population increasing rate mutually and cooperatively. Hence the two aspects may be emphasized and paid attention to in thriving the whole national economic developed degree through enough wielding our generations positively and efficiently by our government institution endeavor and evaluation. For the sake of making relevant policies and allocating capital into the necessary industries the corresponding strategic plan needs to be made under various background and entities. Then the according monitor and estimation will be followed and estimated periodically and frequently by the observer in government's institution. At last as to the developed speed in one nation the corresponding population increasing quantity and high-technique product producing will be discussed and considered more preciously and correctly according to the near past years experience and variation.

Therefore, the high-technique products will be completed through wielding our scientist & senior Engineers coordination tightly for the sake of reviving the industrial and tertiary modernization. We should constantly look for and seek the new quality productivity sustainably so as to take place of our traditional industry becoming modernity. An innovation industry like new energy electric generator will be in front of our path forwards, so that the corresponding tactic must be put up and seek the opportunity and fortune in order to burden our responsibility quickly and not to forget recommend the fitting one to appoint new occupation. Like the Bole identified horse or Maosui self-recommended the recommendation will be represent one aspect for our human resource department to consider and evaluate the recommended included a full research room with a set of computer high-technique instrument & device, subordinate, subsidiary staff, salary, house, welfare etc. a series of work so as to appoint his new occupation reasonably and willingly. [1~20]

2. Discussions

For the sake of welcoming the demand we should educate a lot of scientist and experts candidates from university department to college & institution one to take the

high scholar degree for them to grasp one foreign language and skill to apply to futural requirement and practice. In university, the class with taking more practice education and experience and good teacher proceed the more competition teaching and theoretical and practical combination class to prepare for using after their graduate from college. Meantime, the enhancing GDP factors will include the high-technique products and its whole industrial chains and high-intelligence product that may influence the service business mostly. So we should increase those high-profit & high-tech skill for making more advance products so as to improve our service business level and quality & effectiveness at all. So that we should maintain and develop the tertiary industry continuously under controlling the second one. With the life quality enhancing continually the service one is about to wield its effectiveness presently and in futural long time, thereby we should follow up the changed situation and own independent capacity to master one outstanding skill to satisfy the futural request in advance.

2.1 The USA GDP variation status

The USA GDP with top five sates' variation status analysis would show 317~260 billion yuan by Massachusetts~Washington states accordingly explained the Massachusetts one strong economy strength and capacity in 2003 in light of Figure 1. The y-y value might indicate 4.2%~4.8% by them respectively recorded their modest growth step. In contrast, the Virginia one maintained the fastest step with 6.3%.

Figure 1. The USA GDP with top eleven~fourteen sates' variation status analysis. [1]

Moreover, the USA GDP with top five states' variation status analysis would show 235~210 billion yuan by Maryland~Missouri states accordingly explained their moderate economy strength and capacity in 2003 in light of Figure 2. The y-y value might indicate 6.3%~5% by them respectively recorded their modest growth step. In contrast, the Indiana one maintained the fastest step with 6.9%.

Figure 2. The USA GDP with top fifteen~eighteen states' variation status analysis. [1]

2.2 China provinces' income per capita in 2025

The China top 11 provinces' income per capita variation analysis in 2025 would show 35~42 thousand yuan by Shan'xi & Inner Mongolia respectively expressed their higher income in light of Figure 3. Moreover, all of those top 11 provinces surpassed the whole country average 3.5 thousand.

Figure 3. The China top 11 provinces' income per capita variation analysis in 2025. [2]

Meanwhile ,the China top 12~22 provinces' income per capita variation analysis in 2025 would show 28.3~35 thousand yuan by Gansu & Ningxia provinces respectively expressed their high income in light of Figure 4. Moreover, all of those Ningxia province surpassed the whole country average 3.5 thousand.

Figure 4. The China top 12~22 provinces' income per capita variation analysis in 2025. [2]

2.3 The USA GDP variation status I

The USA GDP with top three states' variation status analysis would show 118~66 billion yuan by California~Texas states accordingly explained the California one strong economy strength and capacity in 1970 in light of Figure 1. The y-y value might indicate 8.3%~16.6% by them respectively recorded their forward growth step.

Figure 5. The USA GDP with top five states' variation status analysis. [1]

Furthermore, the USA GDP with top states' variation status analysis would show 66~33 billion yuan by Illinois~Florida states accordingly explained the Illinois one strong economy strength and capacity in 1970 in light of Figure 6. The y-y value might indicate 7%~15.5% by them respectively recorded their forward growth step.

Figure 6. The USA GDP six~ten states' variation status analysis. [1]

Moreover, the USA GDP with top states' variation status analysis would show 129~132 billion yuan by Minnesota~Missouri states accordingly explained the Illinois one strong economy strength and capacity in 1994 in light of Figure 7. The y-y value might indicate 7%~6.5% by them respectively recorded their modest growth step.

Figure 7. The USA GDP states' variation analysis I. [1]

At the end, the USA GDP with top states' variation status analysis would show 820~530 billion yuan by California~New York states accordingly explained the California one strong economy strength and capacity in 1992 in light of Figure 8. The y-y value might indicate 5%~3.6% by them respectively recorded their moderate growth step.

Figure 8. The USA GDP states' status analysis II. [1]

3. Conclusions

The USA GDP with top five states' variation status analysis would show 317~260 billion yuan by Massachusetts~Washington states accordingly explained the Massachusetts one strong economy strength and capacity in 2003 in light of this paper. The y-y value might indicate 4.2%~4.8% by them respectively recorded their modest growth step. In contrast, the Virginia one maintained the fastest step with 6.3%. On the other side, the China top 11 provinces' income per capita variation analysis in 2025 would show 35~42 thousand yuan by Shan'xi & Inner Mongolia respectively expressed their higher income. Moreover, all of those top 11 provinces surpassed the whole country average 3.5 thousand. Thereby, the high-tech production would occupy the most part for us to be pursuit the high-efficiency and high-level environment that might become our further destination for producing more innovation production continually. So that the enough educating new engineer and talents enable us to process more space for searching more functional ones with more diversities business. Because those diversities may make our life to become more

convenient and comfortable through endeavoring our engineers and experts for the sake of positively participating their each research theme and making an interesting conception under main principles. In USA the more sophisticated project will affect their GDP enhancement through widely collecting the world top scientists and scholars to process more deepening research and science that may occupy their first-one country with stabilized leading effectiveness. From California to Missouri state the higher GDP would reflect the entire nation quality and level through the aeronautics out-space exploration lunar landing etc. a series of scientific research are able to continually process that makes the USA to become No. 1 in all of the fields. Even they proceeded the Mars etc. approaching and rotating & landing works many years ago. Moreover, they owned the most amount nuclear bombs with several thousand that may destroy the whole earth once the nuclear war happens. So we should pay more attention to the USA who may affect its role in every aspects in the earth. Thereby, China will raise up becoming the second GDP big country who may prohibit USA military and scientific development and enlarging behavior too.

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